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Research Article

**A CROSS-SECTIONAL RESEARCH TO ASSESS THE
RELIABILITY AND EFFECTIVENESS OF FNAC (FINE
NEEDLE ASPIRATION CYTOLOGY) AMONG BREAST LUMP
PATIENTS****¹Mishal Saleem, ²Muhammad Ibrahim, ²Shehroz Rehman**
¹UHS, Lahore, ²Islamabad Medical and Dental College**Abstract**

Objective: The objective of this research is to assess the FNAC (Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology) diagnostic accuracy among breast lump patients with the help of a gold standard histopathology.

Material and Methods: We conducted this cross-sectional research at Services Hospital, Lahore (Surgical Department) in the timeframe of February to November 2017. The research sample comprised of 200 breast lump patients.

Results: In the total of 200 breast lump patients the factor of mean age was (35.45 ± 8.57) years. Various age groups were made out of the total research sample. The age bracket of (20 – 30) years included 90 patients (45%), the age bracket of (31 – 40) years included 47 patients (23.5%), the age bracket of (41 – 50) years included 32 patients (16%), the age bracket of (51 – 60) years included 29 patients (14.5%) and lastly above sixty years included 2 patients (1%). Among two hundred patients 7 patients were male (3.5%) and 193 patients were female (96.5%). The outcomes of histopathology of breast lesions reflected 53 malignant cases (26.5%) and 147 benign cases (73.5%). Outcomes reflected FNAC as gold standards for histopathological outcomes. Forty-nine patients were TP (True Positive) (24.5%), sixteen patients were FP (False Positive) (8%), eight patients were FN (False Negative) (4%) and 127 patients were TN (True Negative) (63.5%). The values of sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive values (PPV & NPV) were respectively 85.96%, 88.81%, 75.38% and 94.07%.

Conclusion: FNAC (Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology) diagnostic accuracy among breast lump patients is undoubtedly a gold standard diagnostic tool with greater specificity and sensitivity, cost-effective and less invasive diagnostic procedure.

Keywords: Diagnostic Accuracy, Breast Lump, FNAC (Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology), Specificity and Sensitivity.

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INTRODUCTION:

Women are most commonly involved in the onset of breast cancer in both underdeveloped and developed countries. Developing countries face higher death rates because of breast cancer. Back in 2012, breast cancer was reported 1.7 million patients and half of these patients with death occurred in the underdeveloped countries. OPDs of Pakistan have a regular input of the breast lumps patients. Majority of the patients are of benign (90%) with no severe complications; whereas, malignancy attributes in the palpable lump's significant percentage [1]. Improved outcomes are possible if the onset of breast lumps is diagnosed at an early stage. Diagnosis is confident among ninety-five percent of the patients with triple assessment strategy that includes histological, imaging and examination studies. FNAC is a valuable and essential palpable breast lesion assessment because it is reliable, simple, less complicated and economical mass lesions assessment strategy [2]. In the absence of an adequate sample, the technique is repeatable with a sensitivity in the range of (80% – 98%) and specificity of (99%) [3]. Therefore, the objective of this research is to assess the FNAC (Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology) diagnostic accuracy among breast lump patients with the help of a gold standard histopathology.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

We conducted this cross-sectional research at Services Hospital, Lahore (Surgical Department) in the timeframe of February to November 2017. The research sample comprised of 200 breast lump patients. We did not include any patient with breast cellulitis, breast cysts and breast abscess. Every patient gave an informed consent about the research

protocols. FNAC was conducted by an experienced investigator having three years of experience. We carried out an excision biopsy for lumps and tumours which were benign on FNAC and mastectomy histopathology. The specimen will also be used for onward diagnosis of the tissue. We documented every relevant data on a proforma.

Research used SPSS software for statistical analysis. We presented age in the value of Mean \pm S.D. Whereas, gender distribution was shown in frequency and percentage.

RESULTS:

In the total of 200 breast lump patients, the factor of mean age was (35.45 \pm 8.57) years. Various age groups were made out of the total research sample. The age bracket of (20 – 30) years included 90 patients (45%), the age bracket of (31 – 40) years included 47 patients (23.5%), the age bracket of (41 – 50) years included 32 patients (16%), the age bracket of (51 – 60) years included 29 patients (14.5%) and lastly above sixty years included 2 patients (1%) (Table – I). Among two hundred patients 7 patients were male (3.5%) and 193 patients were female (96.5%). The outcomes of histopathology of breast lesions reflected 53 malignant cases (26.5%) and 147 benign cases (73.5%) (Table – I). Outcomes reflected FNAC as gold standards for histopathological outcomes. Forty-nine patients were TP (True Positive) (24.5%), sixteen patients were FP (False Positive) (8%), eight patients were FN (False Negative) (4%) and 127 patients were TN (True Negative) (63.5%). The values of sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive values (PPV & NPV) were respectively 85.96%, 88.81%, 75.38% and 94.07% (Table – II).

Table – I: Age, Gender and Breast Lesions Stratification

Age, Gender and Breast Lesions		Number	Percentage
Age (Years)	20 – 30 Years	90	45.00
	31 – 40 Years	47	23.50
	41 – 50 Years	32	16.00
	51 – 60 Years	29	14.50
	> 60 Years	2	1.00
Gender	Male	7	3.00
	Female	193	97.00
Breast Lesions	Malignant	53	26.50
	Benign	147	73.50

Table – II: FNAC Outcomes

FNAC Outcomes	Positive		Negative		Total	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Positive	49	24.5	16	8	65	32.5
Negative	8	4	127	63.5	135	67.5
Total	57	28.5	143	71.5	200	100

DISCUSSION:

Breast lump FNAC is cost-effective, safe and excellent diagnostic method that requires minimum and less expensive instruments with simple operating procedure [4]. The procedure is executable anywhere including clinic, the office of the physician and at the bed of the patient. Its significant merits include less invasiveness, rapid outcomes and accurate outcomes in comparison to the outcomes of biopsy of the tissues. Breast lump FNAC procedures are capable enough to reduce the onset of open breast biopsies

[5].

The outcomes of histopathology of breast lesions reflected 53 malignant cases (26.5%) and 147 benign cases (73.5%). Outcomes reflected FNAC as gold standards for histopathological outcomes. Forty-nine patients were TP (True Positive) (24.5%), sixteen patients were FP (False Positive) (8%), eight patients were FN (False Negative) (4%) and 127 patients were TN (True Negative) (63.5%). The values of sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive values (PPV & NPV) were respectively

85.96%, 88.81%, 75.38% and 94.07%.

Various other studies have also shown outcomes about FP in the bracket of (0% – 2%) and for FN in the bracket of (7% – 22%) [6, 7]. Various reasons for the sampling errors are reported cytologists' intraoperative errors and microscopic errors [8]. The suspicious outcomes are in the range of (3% – 18%) [9]. The suspicious outcomes as per the outcomes of Kamal are (3.39%) [10].

Among both biopsy and FNAC procedure, the number of benign cases was 32 and one case of fibrocystic disease whereas one FNAC case became malignant. We reported the specificity and sensitivity of FNAC respectively as 96.96% and 91.66%; whereas, according to Heber and Ch T the specificity and sensitivity values were respectively (100% & 93.10%) and (88.46% & 85.13%) [7, 11]. Other studies reported the same as (96.8% & 93%) and (100% & 96.42%) [12, 13]. Literature review presents specificity as 100% and sensitivity as (80% – 98%) [14].

False negative outcomes also have an association with dysplasia [15]. False negative outcomes may also have an association with tumours and histological forms such as mucinous, lobular carcinoma, tubular carcinoma or medullary carcinoma [16]. FNAC is a simple method to assess breast lesions. The overall FNAC outcomes are totally dependent on lump size, investigator experience and cytologists experience. FNAC presents higher accuracy with effective diagnostic strategy [17].

CONCLUSION:

We recommend FNAC for breast lumps diagnosis to decide a definite therapy. FNAC (Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology) diagnostic accuracy among breast lump patients is undoubtedly a gold standard diagnostic tool with greater specificity and sensitivity, cost-effective and less invasive diagnostic procedure.

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